
PLAGIARISM CONCEPT: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract:

Today, considering the worldwide research, the work of promoting research is being done in all fields today. Research has always been an important factor for the development and progress of human society. Research and innovation are being encouraged today from daily necessities to space exploration. New research is being done in the fields of social sciences, science and commerce. However, while this research is being done, some wrong trends are also coming into the field of research. Have come One of the most important trends is literalism. This concept came forward intensively through research. Plagiarism is content that is copied or plagiarized from literature, books and online reference tools. It means eloquence.

Plagiarism is the complete or necessary alteration of an original literary work of an author and published by another author under his own name and pretending to be his own. In the fields of research, Plagiarism is no longer a problem of college researchers, teachers and university sector in modern times. Today this problem is faced in all sectors. Even in the world of professional, industrial and newspaper writing, the two problems of writing and attribution are being faced in a severe manner today. The main purpose of conducting research in the context of the concept of Plagiarism is to make students and researchers aware of the concept of Plagiarism whatever the research may be, if the author implements these two things, regularity and reliability, the problem of literary corruption that the world is facing today can be reduced.

Keyword: History of the Plagiarism, Plagiarism, Reasons of Plagiarism, Exception of Plagiarism, Types of Plagiarism, Plagiarism Detection Tools, Urkund, Turnitin.

Introduction:

Creating research is the creativity of the writer. Previous literature has to be used for research. In the creation of new research, a comprehensive review of what has been written in the context of the same topic in the previous period is done. You want to review the literature in terms of gaps in the new research. It is considered appropriate to refer to the said literature. But knowingly or unknowingly if we do

not mention it then it is called as punctuation. As you know theft is taking possession of another person's property. It is illegal, similarly, in the literary world, the act of publishing an original literary work of an author in whole or in part by another author under his own name and pretending to be his own is called plagiarism. In simple words, Plagiarism means deceiving the readers/society by

claiming that someone else's literary work is your own.

Vangamaychaurya and Shreyachaurya are two separate concepts. They can be distinguished but they cannot be separated from each other. At the root of both is the same concept of theft. Sometimes literature is directly plagiarized. Sometimes credit for their creation is stolen. In Sanskrit or Marathi or similar Indian languages a distinction is found between Vangamaychaurya and Shreyachaurya. But in English, this difference is not known. Plagiarism is a single word or term used in English to refer to plagiarism and plagiarism.

History of the Plagiarism Concept:

According to the Oxford dictionary, the word plagiarism is derived from the Latin word PLAGIARE. It means Kidnap. The first use of the word is mentioned in Latin as Plagius by a Roman poet between 40 AD and 102-104 AD in the context of an unnamed literary thief of poem. Thief in Literature one who kills the thought or writings of another the crime of literary theft is defined as.

According to the Oxford Dictionary, the English term "plagiarism" has its roots in the ancient Greek word "plageion". Plagiarus in Latin means thief. Plagiarism in Indo-European language plage means net or snare. The term plagiarism came to mean plagiarism, meaning any secret act, to plagiarize a literary work, since plagiarism became the operative form in the sense of ensnaring someone.

Greek Latin then "plagiarism" began its journey to English. In 1601, the playwright Ben Jonson coined the term plagiarism to mean plagiarism. The term plagiarism was adopted in English thought around 1620. Samuel Johnson in his

dictionary published in 1755 defined "plagiarism" as "A theft in literature one who kills the thought or writings of another the crime of literary theft".

Plagiarus is the Latin word used by the ancient Roman poet Martial when he complained that his poem had been plagiarized by his rival Fidentius. Critic Jack Lynch opines that the term plagiarism may have been coined because the language fits perfectly into the world and the world of thought.

What is Plagiarism?

Merriam Webster of Indian dictionary lega is an act of using another person's world or ideas without giving a Credit to the person." Publishing an original literary work of an author in whole or in part by another author under his own name and pretending that it is his own is called Plagiarism. Plagiarism author claims to be the creator of the original literary work even though he is not the creator of the original literary work Hiding the original literary work or not mentioning it at all in the adaptation is called Plagiarism.

According to the above definition, there are some types of Plagiarism.

1. Passing off another's writing as one's own.
2. Using someone else's words or ideas without crediting them.
3. Citing another author's work without using quotation marks.
4. Using material by citing wrong source.
5. Using sentence by changing words or copy pasting.
6. Using too many phrases, words or phrases from another author and attributing them as much Information as possible.

From the above discussion it is clear that plagiarism is done through words, sentences, whole chapter, book, source but the reasons why this is done can be given as below.

1. Writers are not aware of their own writing skills or lack writing skills and vocabulary.
2. Ignoring or misinterpreting plagiarism.
3. Laxity of educational institutions which makes students not think in terms of innovation.
4. Lack of referencing skills of the researcher.
5. The materials/articles which are easily available on the internet lead to easy plagiarism.
6. Lack of knowledge of the researcher about the subject.
7. Having a copy-paste attitude in today's academic and research work.
8. Research and plagiarism for future advancement and job requirements as per academic policy.

Exception of Plagiarism:

1. If a literary work is created based on reference tools like history, Puranas, myths, oral folklore, it does not constitute a literary work.
2. If the creation of literature is based on the original content or central idea of a literary work in another language and if the original literary work is mentioned based on the reference literature, it does not constitute literary plagiarism.
3. If two writers come up with the same idea and while writing a story, novel or play based on it, if the same incident is written by both of them, then no one is accused of Plagiarism.
4. Attributes in the field of natural science can suggest the same theory or its basic principle to two

researchers, scientists at the same time in two different places; they have no contact with each other.

5. Some topics and some ideas are common in literature in general and indicative sense. The fact that those ideas and themes are often repeated in the literary work of different authors does not constitute literary merit.
6. In the literary formation of any writer, there is culture of previous and contemporary writers and their literary works. Unknowing imitation of the original content, ideas, technique or layout, style of that literature, usually happens in the early days of the writer. That too cannot be called Plagiarism. However, if it is deliberately imitated or is unvaried, it is necessary to mention the same, otherwise the possibility of it being literal can't be ruled out.
7. Pre-written or pre-published literary works exactly as its content and subject arrangement
8. It is plagiarism if another author has printed it in his own name without mentioning the original article in whole or in part including style.
9. If an author publishes a translation or adaptation of a literary work in a foreign language without the prior consent of the original author and without mentioning the original author and the original literary work in his own name, it also becomes a literary act.

Philosophical side of Plagiarism:

Three children are involved from a philosophical point of view in Plagiarism action.

1. Cognitive
2. Ethical
3. Aesthetic

In modern times, these three value systems have been challenged by Plagiarism and due to this challenge, the field of applied knowledge called "Ethics of Research" has emerged in applied ethics. In a sense, the theory "knowledge is policy" applies here from an epistemological and ethical point of view.

Types of Plagiarism:

Types of Plagiarism in modern times are classified in different ways. Various universities, colleges, educational institutions have their own types of plagiarism and anti-plagiarism rules. All of these are divided into two types: complete plagiarism and unintentional plagiarism. Intentional plagiarism includes self-plagiarism. Often times, a researcher will not be accused of self-plagiarism when he uses his own text from one place but does not refer to the original sources. But it is not epistemic accuracy. However, if the same text intentionally omits the original source in more than one place, it becomes plagiarism. The same rule applies to pictures, videotapes and sound media along with text.

Plagiarism

Writing:

- Copy-paste
- By changing the words
- Stealing ideas
- Wrong source
- Re-Tweet

Based on Program-Code:

- Software
- Programme
- Code

Plagiarism in writing, this is preferably done in academic and literary form.

Copy-Paste: In this, the data is copied and pasted from an online or available source. In this age of social media and fast internet, the amount of plagiarism

of this type of material seems to have increased.

By word change: In this type of plagiarism, plagiarism is done by changing the words in the literature or by changing the sentence structure.

Idea plagiarism: In this, a writer, designer, researcher has created a new idea and telling the same idea under his own name is also a form of plagiarism.

Self-plagiarism: In these forms of plagiarism, repeating the same research again and again with or without modification or publishing it in another place is called self-plagiarism.

False source: In this type, an opinion is made with incorrect or non-existent reference. That is, false information is given about the source.

Re-Tweet Plagiarism: Plagiarism is plagiarism in the social media tool Twitter. Someone else's tweet is rebroadcast in your name.

Program Code Based:

Program code-based plagiarism is plagiarism in the context of computer programs. This includes software, program code, un-authorized use and sometimes sold in violation of copyright. This is called Program Code Based Literacy.

Tools to Stop plagiarism:

Plagiarism happens in research while doing research. To avoid it, we can consider some options. How much literature is there in the research through which we have done. Here are some plagiarism tools that help prevent it. Through which one can help to prevent slander. There are many tools available online and through software to find

spelling. Some of them can be mentioned below.

Plagiarism Detection Tools:

Text Based Tools Education Purpose

Plagaware online search engine
 Plagscan-online software with unique signature
 Check for plagiarism net fingerprint print based approach
 Dupalichekar
 Gramrali
 Scribar

Source Code Based

Moss-Moss-MMeasure of Ssoftware SSimilarity
 Jplag-comare program Series Code Match

Through the above software we can get the percentage of plagiarism in innovation. The lower the percentage of plagiarism, the better the research is said to be. There are also Urkund and Turnitin software for plagiarism detection.

1. Urkund:

Urkund software is based on the web page and is known as Shodh-Shindu as a part of UGC's Shodh-Shindu. All universities in India are provided by INFLIBNET through Software as a Service (SaaS). It shows the percentage of plagiarism in research through databases, books, old assignments and writing based projects created by students. This software is complementary to search in Doc, HTML, PPT, Text File formats.

2. Turnitin:

Through this software used to find out the amount of plagiarism in the research paper given for Ph.D.

Conclusion:

Literacy in terms of epistemology indicates a lack of epistemic integrity. Knowledge is created in the absence of knowledge. There is no authenticity in both rhetoric and lies. A poem is a product of human skill. Thus, in both forgery and fraud, human skill is expressed in such a way that it appears to be genuine despite the rhetoric. Its purpose is to deceive the reader. In the Plagiarism act, the thief wants to pass off the writings of others under his own name. While projected work tries to write his own writings in the name of others. Plagiarism is a highly educated and trained sin.

This is not a philosophical problem. Plagiarism is a breach of ideological discipline and civility. Literacy is more of a legal issue than a theoretical issue. Although plagiarism is not legally a crime, plagiarism is more common in the fields of journalism and education, which are considered morally serious. Students, teachers, professors, researchers, guides are leaders in plagiarism. Today, many laws have been enacted in the twenty-first century. Legal provisions like Accounts Payable, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) etc. are in place in our system. Adjunctive punitive measures such as promotion, demotion of financial benefits and in some cases compulsory discharge etc. have been introduced to prevent fraud. In such cases, social infamy is a huge loss. It is imperative to take note of the new changes in this regard in the present time. In terms of intellectual property rights and protection, the law should be enforced very strictly as in European countries.

A new person who makes an exact copy of another's material and uses it in his own name can be criminalized under the Copyright Act and sentenced to fine or imprisonment. But Plagiarism is an easy

thing in contemporary Internet era. Also adding to the intelligibility, one of the characteristics of theft is theft. But at the same time it can remain unknown. There are two obvious reasons for this. The first is that computer systems for detecting plagiarism have become easier to develop through the medium of the English language. But regional language computing systems are still not available to recognize these characteristics of regional languages.

Computer systems today are still limited to the natural sciences. It has not yet extended to social sciences and psychology and anthropology. Moreover, in natural science journals, the professional discipline of noting when an essay has been published has not yet emerged in other disciplines.

1. The group should try to convey information about literacy at each level.
2. To guide the students on the use of materials.
3. Verifying the authenticity of an article while submitting it.
4. Introducing and demonstrating plagiarism software.
5. The understanding and seriousness of this subject will be known by showing the related video of Plagiarism
6. It is necessary to create more awareness among researchers and students from the point of view of destroying the attitude of Plagiarism.
7. Efforts should be made to ensure that plagiarism does not occur while exchanging materials from the library.

8. Literature related software which is available today at university level and National Institute should be made available in every library.
9. To create awareness among researchers and students in the context of software and literacy with demonstration
10. It is necessary.
11. In the context of Plagiarism as a librarian, research can definitely be useful and productive for the society if librarians provide this kind of guidance.

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